

Towards People Behaviour Prediction with Deep Learning Approach

Fatima ISIAKA

Department of Computer Science Nasarawa State University, Keffi Email : fatima.isiaka@outlook.com

Sophia ARSHAJI

Department of Computer Science Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom

Abstract

Deep learning and pattern recognition are highly relevant to research areas that are commonly used in fields such as behaviour analytics, user interaction, human factors and robotics with artificial intelligence. And despite their overlapping similarities, these similar concepts have nothing in common. In this paper, we discussed its applications in behaviour detection in people, especially in an indiscreet environment with some of the differences in the concepts surrounding the three models of deep learning and their applications to abnormal behaviour tracking in people in an indiscreet environment. The procedures in the mechanisms of Auto-encoder, Decoders, Convolutional Neural network (CNN), and Recurrent Neural network were applied in the motion detection for abnormal behaviour prediction in people the performance in tracker operation characteristics was used to describe the performance rate of each tracking process. The results showed that normal behaviour in people has a more perfect fit to the models than abnormal behaviour patterns; the performance rate in decoders has a regular balance in the tracking phase compared to the other models.

Keywords : Encoders, Decoders, Convolutional neural network, Recurrent Neural network, Behaviour analytics, Pattern recognition

1 Introduction

Deep learning is one of the most investigated research areas in modern AI topics, this is most seen in CNN and RNN which has been used in large-scale graphic recognition [8, 11, 14, 32, 6]. In the concept of deep learning,

there is minimal human intervention and little bias due to the parameters in the modes that it learns from its dataset. Deep learning is best suitable to a large-scale dataset with strong computational capabilities to optimise the modes [30, 9, 28, 16, 4]. Complexity in datasets can be seen in behaviour data since its contents coordinate both visual interface stimuli and biometric measures

for an experiment [24, 25, 15, 18, 12]. Image processing behaviour is also the most complex and can be detected using schematic modules for a given phase in a computational model. Here standard methods are applied in analysing behaviour data with deep learning, including Auto-encoders, Decoders, CNN and RNN, this is discussed in the following sections.

1.1 Auto-Encoders and Decoders

Auto-encoders [20, 29, 31, 3, 22, 19] are a sequential neural network that consists of two different components, an encoder and a decoder (Figure 1). Here, we are dealing with a sequence of the video frame with human characteristics for detecting abnormal and normal behaviour in a person, these video sequences are static images, and the main aim of the encoder is to extract features from the image, thereby reducing the image in height and dimensionality with the width, simultaneously growing it in depth. The encoder makes a latent representation of the image by pooling in a convolutional trend. The decoders aim to decode the latent representation and form an image that satisfies the model's given criterion, by un-pooling and deconvolution trends. The input matrix represents the dataset with the attributes, with a given epoch or set of epochs the matrix is decoded to an outer layer containing the resultant matrix.

1.2 Recurrent neural network

The Recurrent neural networks (RNN) [26, 23, 10, 7, 21] are where each node in each layer is connected in the form of a directed graph along a certain temporal sequence, they are meant to exhibit temporal dynamic behaviour. RNNs can use their memory state to process variable-length sequences of inputs for the behaviour data. RNN is used indiscriminately to two a broad class of network connectivity using a similar generalized structure, in this case, one of them is a finite impulse while the other is an infinite impulse. Each of these classes exhibits temporal physical dynamic behaviour. The finite impulse of recurrent network structure is a form of a directed acyclic graph which can be unrolled and is replaced by a strict feed-forward network, the infinite impulse is a network structure that forms a direct cyclic graph which can be unrolled. In both cases, the recurrent networks can have an additional set of stored states and this stored state can be under direct control by the neural network structure. Also, the storage can be replaced by another kind of network of a directed graph, if it incorporates latency or a feedback loop. This is referred to as gated memory. It is also part of a long short-term gated state with gated recurrent units which can also be a Feedback Neural Network. The structure above is used to generate another set of the residual vector from the behaviour data $x_r \dots x_r^{(n)}$, as user attributes and hidden

layers $A_r \dots A_r^{(t+1)}$ (Figure 2) as the epochs between 1-10.

2 Convolutional Neural Network

The original goal of CNN is to take the input image and produce a set of bounding boxes as output, where each bounding box contains an object and also the category of the object from a set of databases, for this case in the parallel set, only three images are allowed for the best fit for images close the input image matrix. This process used a set length L_{loc} for its location for a set of input images in the parallel reduction module (Equations 1 and 2), where t and v are the time and distance from every smooth search. More recently [5, 2, 13, 17, 27, 1], CNN has been extended to perform other computational tasks such as user demography information and a system performance check for authentication of the summary information about an individual. The following covers some of the versions of CNN that have been developed

$$L_{loc}(t^u, v) = \sum_{i \in \{x, y, w, h\}}^{n} smooth_{L_1}(t_1 - v_i),$$

$$\text{where } smooth_{L_1}(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5x^2 & \text{if } |x| \leq 1 \\ |x| - 0.5 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \downarrow x_m = 2x_{out} + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module} \rightarrow m \\ \downarrow x_{out} \end{array} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \downarrow x_{m0} = 2x_{m-1} + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module}_m \\ \downarrow x_{m-1} = 2x_{m-2} + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module}_{(m-1)} \downarrow \\ \vdots \\ \downarrow x_1 = 2x_0 + 1 \\ \text{Reduction module}_1 \\ \downarrow x_0 \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{x_{m+1}}{x_{m-1+1}} = 2 \\ \frac{x_{m-1+1}}{x_{m-2+1}} = 2 \\ \vdots \\ \frac{x_1+1}{x_0+1} = 2 \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\rightarrow x_m = 2^m x_0 + 2^m 2(m \in M) \quad (2)$$

The example of the system design in this paper shows how to automatically detect and track human abnormal behaviour using the main feature points like body gestures and poses in a discreet environment. The approach in this paper keeps track of a person even when the person tilts his or her head or moves toward or away from a surveillance camera.

3 Method

The method adopted for human behaviour tracking is based on the standard approach discussed above. Each

FIGURE 1 – Framework and model architecture of Auto-Encoders and Decoders.

FIGURE 2 – The architectural framework for recurrent neural networks on behaviour data.

of these processes has similar characteristics that distinguish them from the normal sequence of object tracking. This is one of the many modern technologies touched by deep learning on surveillance. The integration of deep learning concepts on video surveillance for tracking behaviour patterns represents a remarkable change in security advancement. It makes the concept of surveillance more powerful and accurate than before. Auto-encoders augment security integration systems by providing a greater ability to synthesize and react to the input data in real time. This is increased security and more ingenious applications for advanced technology. This brings more

advantages to video surveillance and easier to operate.

Deep learning makes smart video surveillance which relies on the ability and accuracy to access multiple personalities in a dynamic scene. The ability of the deep learners to rapidly analyse a scene searches for anomalous behaviour much faster. It attempts to determine when behaviour falls out of bounds for what is expected at a target point. Motion anomaly detection relies on data analytics to provide autonomous situational awareness. This paper uses the concept of motion detection with deep learning to track the normal behaviour of people and differentiate them from abnormal behaviour. Pre-

FIGURE 3 – Convolutional neural network framework on behaviour data.

vious work normally uses auto-encoders to track people by simply moving in an indiscreet environment, advancement has made tracking of every single person to be subjected to check review on a repository of “normal behaviour”. The result is higher in detecting abnormal situations with high risk. The following section discusses the results obtained from using the deep learning models on behaviour data.

4 Result

Figure 4 shows an interface of a video sequence of detected normal and abnormal behaviour of people. The features characteristics for detecting abnormal behaviour in an indiscreet environment are carrying a piece of heavy luggage with an uncomfortable posture, running, bending and unusual hand gestures the model is trained to detect such features and predict the patterns based on the classified attributes, for this case an unsupervised method is adopted. The maximum risk location for every point detected is set to alert provided the estimated level is exceeded. The estimated level is less than four times for a detected location.

The performance score for each of the deep learning models used in the work is tested using the tracker operating characters which reports on the true positive rate and false-positive rate. Figure 5 shows the performances and error rates of the models on five different epochs for the four models used. The decoder is used to compare the resulting image for a detected video sequence containing abnormal and normal behaviour patterns of people to its input mode. This is done using five different epochs for each model. The result shows that the performance for

the output sequence is far more accurate and consistent with each other than the other models. CNN on different epoch also shows a consistent pattern with all five epochs. Epochs are chosen between 1 and 10 with a rationale for natural sequences in the visual output.

Performance is also tested on the residual out of both normal and abnormal behaviour of the people. The performance on tracking normal behaviour is more accurate at 0.99% than abnormal behaviour at 0.95%. The accuracy shows that normal behaviour is more in the population than abnormal behaviour, this is also normal and agrees with the natural occurrence of events. Given that the number of instances in the dataset is less than a thousand, the result might not be feasible enough to agree to a plausible conclusion, hence an authentic assumption can be made when the model is detected on larger datasets.

5 Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the use of deep learning techniques in an attempt at pattern recognition in behaviour analytics. We looked at its applications in behaviour detection in people, especially in an indiscreet environment with some of the differences in the concepts surrounding the three models of deep learning and their applications to abnormal behaviour tracking in people in an indiscreet environment. The procedures in the mechanisms of Auto-encoder, Decoders, Convolutional Neural network (CNN) and Recurrent Neural network were applied in the motion detection for abnormal behaviour prediction in people the performance in tracker operation characteristics was used to describe the performance rate

FIGURE 4 – : Window interface of detected individuals with abnormal and normal behaviour in an indiscreet environment.

FIGURE 5 – Performane rate of tracker on all four deep learning methods.

of each tracking process. The results showed that normal behaviour in people has a more perfect fit to the models than abnormal behaviour patterns and the performance rate in decoders has a regular balance in the tracking phase compared to the other models. The future perspective to these procedures is to utilise larger data-

sets for a more robust pattern search for a more feasible conclusion.

FIGURE 6 – Performance rate on the two most significant models..

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Nasarawa State University, Keffi Nigeria and Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom for the sponsor of this paper.

Références

- [1] Abdulnabi, A. H., Wang, G., Lu, J., and Jia, K. (2015). Multi-task cnn model for attribute prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 17(11):1949–1959.
- [2] Alzubaidi, L., Zhang, J., Humaidi, A. J., Al-Dujaili, A., Duan, Y., Al-Shamma, O., Santamara, J., Fadhel, M. A., Al-Amidie, M., and Farhan, L. (2021). Review of deep learning : concepts, cnn architectures, challenges, applications, future directions. *Journal of big Data*, 8 :1–74.
- [3] Baccouche, M., Mamalet, F., Wolf, C., Garcia, C., and Baskurt, A. (2012). Spatio-temporal convolutional sparse auto-encoder for sequence classification. In *BMVC*, pages 1–12.
- [4] Bassel, G. W., Glaab, E., Marquez, J., Holdsworth, M. J., and Bacardit, J. (2011). Functional network construction in arabidopsis using rule-based machine learning on large-scale data sets. *The Plant Cell*, 23(9) :3101–3116.
- [5] Bhatt, D., Patel, C., Talsania, H., Patel, J., Vaghela, R., Pandya, S., Modi, K., and Ghayvat, H. (2021). Cnn variants for computer vision : History, architecture, application, challenges and future scope. *Electronics*, 10(20) :2470.
- [6] Borisyuk, F., Gordo, A., and Sivakumar, V. (2018). Rosetta : Large scale system for text detection and recognition in images. In *Proceedings of the 24th ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery & data mining*, pages 71–79.
- [7] Dhruv, P. and Naskar, S. (2020). Image classification using convolutional neural network (cnn) and recurrent neural network (rnn) : A review. *Machine learning and information processing : proceedings of ICMLIP 2019*, pages 367–381.
- [8] Dutta, K., Krishnan, P., Mathew, M., and Jawahar, C. (2018). Improving cnn-rnn hybrid networks for handwriting recognition. In *2018 16th international conference on frontiers in handwriting recognition (ICFHR)*, pages 80–85. IEEE.
- [9] El Hmimdi, A. E., Kapoula, Z., and Sainte Fare Garnot, V. (2024). Deep learning-based detection of learning disorders on a large scale dataset of eye movement records. *BioMedInformatics*, 4(1) :519–541.
- [10] Grossberg, S. (2013). Recurrent neural networks. *Scholarpedia*, 8(2) :1888.
- [11] Guo, Y., Liu, Y., Bakker, E. M., Guo, Y., and Lew, M. S. (2018). Cnn-rnn : a large-scale hierarchical image classification framework. *Multimedia tools and applications*, 77(8) :10251–10271.
- [12] Holland, C. D. and Komogortsev, O. V. (2013). Complex eye movement pattern biometrics : The effects of environment and stimulus. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 8(12) :2115–2126.
- [13] Kim, H., Nam, H., Jung, W., and Lee, J. (2017). Performance analysis of cnn frameworks for gpus. In *2017 IEEE International Symposium on Performance Analysis of Systems and Software (ISPASS)*, pages 55–64. IEEE.
- [14] Kollias, D. and Zafeiriou, S. (2020). Exploiting multi-cnn features in cnn-rnn based dimensional emotion recognition on the omg in-the-wild dataset. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 12(3) :595–606.
- [15] Krajina, A. (2022). From the attention to the recall : looking behind online consumer response. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 41(16) :3399–3414.
- [16] Li, J., Hui, B., Qu, G., Yang, J., Li, B., Li, B., Wang, B., Qin, B., Geng, R., Huo, N., et al. (2024). Can llm already serve as a database interface ? a big bench for large-scale database grounded text-to-sqls. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36.
- [17] Li, L., Ota, K., and Dong, M. (2018). Sustainable cnn for robotic : An offloading game in the 3d vision computation. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Computing*, 4(1) :67–76.

- [18] Liebers, J., Horn, P., Burschik, C., Gruenefeld, U., and Schneegass, S. (2021). Using gaze behavior and head orientation for implicit identification in virtual reality. In *Proceedings of the 27th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology*, pages 1–9.
- [19] Liu, Z., He, Y., Cen, H., and Lu, R. (2018). Deep feature representation with stacked sparse auto-encoder and convolutional neural network for hyperspectral imaging-based detection of cucumber defects. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 61(2) :425–436.
- [20] Mezaache, H. and Bouzgou, H. (2018). Auto-encoder with neural networks for wind speed forecasting. In *2018 International Conference on Communications and Electrical Engineering (ICCEE)*, pages 1–5. IEEE.
- [21] Nanduri, A. and Sherry, L. (2016). Anomaly detection in aircraft data using recurrent neural networks (rnn). In *2016 Integrated Communications Navigation and Surveillance (ICNS)*, pages 5C2–1. Ieee.
- [22] Nguyen, D., Nguyen, D. T., Zeng, R., Nguyen, T. T., Tran, S. N., Nguyen, T., Sridharan, S., and Fookes, C. (2021). Deep auto-encoders with sequential learning for multimodal dimensional emotion recognition. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 24 :1313–1324.
- [23] Pascanu, R., Gulcehre, C., Cho, K., and Bengio, Y. (2013). How to construct deep recurrent neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv :1312.6026*.
- [24] Pfeuffer, K., Geiger, M. J., Prange, S., Mecke, L., Buschek, D., and Alt, F. (2019). Behavioural biometrics in vr : Identifying people from body motion and relations in virtual reality. In *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 1–12.
- [25] Rigas, I., Economou, G., and Fotopoulos, S. (2012). Biometric identification based on the eye movements and graph matching techniques. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 33(6) :786–792.
- [26] Sherstinsky, A. (2020). Fundamentals of recurrent neural network (rnn) and long short-term memory (lstm) network. *Physica D : Nonlinear Phenomena*, 404 :132306.
- [27] Shin, H.-C., Roth, H. R., Gao, M., Lu, L., Xu, Z., Nogues, I., Yao, J., Mollura, D., and Summers, R. M. (2016). Deep convolutional neural networks for computer-aided detection : Cnn architectures, dataset characteristics and transfer learning. *IEEE transactions on medical imaging*, 35(5) :1285–1298.
- [28] Wang, T., Wang, L., Zhang, X., Shen, C., Zhang, O., Wang, J., Wu, J., Jin, R., Zhou, D., Chen, S., et al. (2024). Comprehensive assessment of protein loop modeling programs on large-scale datasets : prediction accuracy and efficiency. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 25(1) :bbad486.
- [29] Wang, Y., Yao, H., and Zhao, S. (2016). Auto-encoder based dimensionality reduction. *Neurocomputing*, 184 :232–242.
- [30] Xu, Z., Gong, Y., Zhou, Y., Bao, Q., and Qian, W. (2024). Enhancing kubernetes automated scheduling with deep learning and reinforcement techniques for large-scale cloud computing optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv :2403.07905*.
- [31] Zhang, B., Zhang, H., Zhao, G., and Lian, J. (2020). Constructing a pm2. 5 concentration prediction model by combining auto-encoder with bi-lstm neural networks. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 124 :104600.
- [32] Zhu, X., Li, L., Zhang, W., Rao, T., Xu, M., Huang, Q., and Xu, D. (2017). Dependency exploitation : A unified cnn-rnn approach for visual emotion recognition. In *IJCAI*, pages 3595–3601.